

Assessing Household Vulnerability to Food Insecurity and Coping Strategies in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

This study investigated the incidence of food insecurity vulnerability and the coping strategies employed among farming households in Nigeria, with a panel dataset spanning from year 2012 to 2018. Using a Correlated Random Effects (CRE) model across three waves, the study assessed the factors determining households' vulnerability to food insecurity over time. Key findings from the Fixed Effects model indicated that higher dependency ratios and increased spending on purchased food items elevated households' food expenditure, while flooding was also found to have a dampening effect. The CRE model revealed that larger households and older household heads consistently have higher food expenditures, while access to formal credit, access to agricultural extension services, and mode of land acquisition significantly reduced expenditure in the long term. Environmental factors, such as poor rainfall and flooding also impact food costs significantly, which underscore the financial burden of climate shocks. Despite various coping strategies such as reduction in food quality and skipping meals, mild to moderate food insecurity situations remain prevalent, affecting less than 50% of households, which points to a persistent food insecurity among Nigerian households, with a slight reduction in vulnerability due to Progress in agricultural practices. Consequent on the findings, this study underscores the critical need for targeted interventions to enhance resilience and food security status among the vulnerable farming communities in the study area.

Key words: *Vulnerability, Food insecurity, Coping strategies, Correlated Random Effect.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Food is a fundamental requirement for human well-being and productivity, and this remains an indispensable prerequisite for the survival of humankind and its economic activities. Attaining a sustainable food security has been a major challenge, especially in developing countries, and this has been prioritized as a basic human right (Ajayi and Olutumise, 2017). According to the World Food Summit (2017), "food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food, which meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life." Achieving food security is one of the primary goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable development. However, ensuring global food security remains a great challenge due to the complexities of climatic, environmental, socio-economic and institutional factors across different scales (FAO, 2018).

Being food secure is a basic human right, yet owing to various social, economic, and environmental disparities, more than 850 million people face food insecurity, approximately 12% of the total world's population (Pollard and Booth, 2019; United Nations, 2023). According to Olawuyi and Ijila, 2023, one of the most significant challenges facing the global population, particularly in developing nations, is the lack of access to adequate, nutritious food. This issue is exacerbated by the frequent and diverse socio-economic, ecological, and environmental disruptions that people experience (Ansah, *et al.*, 2019; Hertel, *et al.*, 2021). The severity of climate-related shocks is intensifying due to ongoing environmental degradation, and resource-constrained farmers often lack the means to mitigate these impacts effectively. The consequences of these various shocks on food security are substantial, resulting in significant welfare costs. As a result, both humanitarian organizations and development policy experts have focused their attention on creating appropriate interventions at multiple levels to address these challenges (Hertel, *et al.*, 2021; Olawuyi and Ijila, 2023).

FAO (2010) defines food insecurity as the consequences of inadequate consumption of nutritious food bearing in mind that the physiological use of food is within the domain of nutrition and health. Food insecurity negatively impacts physical and mental health as well as educational and economic outcomes, and as a result acts as a key barrier to socioeconomic development (FAO, *et al.*, 2018; Gundersen and Ziliak, 2015). Furthermore, floods and other extreme weather events can impact food security by damaging agricultural land and assets; destroying food storage infrastructure, roads, and transport networks and increasing the transmission of waterborne diseases that limit the ability for individual to absorb nutrients from food (Vermeulen, Campbell, and Ingram, 2012; Wheeler and Von Braun, 2013). According to Abimbola and Kayode (2013), a large proportion of Nigeria households are still food insecure despite the several efforts by successive governments to achieve food security through setting up of various agricultural development institutions, programme and projects. Low household agricultural productivity and

associated low income have resulted in persistent food insecurity particularly in the rural and low income urban households. Nigeria, Africa's most populous country with over 160 million people, faces significant challenges in food security and economic stability, where agriculture forms the backbone of its economy, contributing around 40% to the GDP (Abdullah, 2017; Devereux, 2018). However, Ashagidigbi *et al.* (2017) noted that more than half of the population lacks access to basic amenities, and many households, especially those with women and children, are not food secure. This reinforces the submission by Olomola (2017) that food insecurity remains a fundamental challenge in Nigeria with malnutrition spreading rapidly among its population, where many households are vulnerable to chronic food shortages, poor food quality, unstable food supply, and fluctuating food prices (FAO *et al.*, 2018). These issues are further exacerbated by high rates of poverty, unemployment, and malnutrition, particularly among vulnerable groups (Andam *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, the study provides answers to the following research questions:

- What are the effects of vulnerability to food insecurity on household farmers in Nigeria?
- What are the coping strategies to food insecurity in Nigeria?

2. INSIGHTS FROM THE EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Sileshi *et al.*, (2019) examined the analysis of households' vulnerability to food insecurity and its influencing factors in East Hararghe, Ethiopia. The study used vulnerability as expected poverty (VEP) approach and Feasible General Least Squares regression model to analyze vulnerability to food insecurity of farming households and the factors which influenced vulnerability to food insecurity. The results revealed that vulnerability to food insecurity increased with the age of household head ($P < 0.1$), and family size ($P < 0.01$). It decreased with access to improved seeds ($P < 0.01$), adoption of soil and water conservation ($P < 0.01$), size of cultivated land ($P < 0.1$), and access to credits ($P < 0.1$). Based on the intensity of their vulnerability, households were grouped as chronic food insecure (24.27%), transient food insecure (11.77%), highly vulnerable-food secure (18.38%), and low vulnerable-food secure (45.59%). Overall, about 54% of households were categorized as vulnerable to food insecurity. Zemedu and Mesfi (2014) investigate smallholders' vulnerability to food insecurity and coping strategies: In the face of climate change, East Hararghe, Ethiopia. The study analyzed the food security status of households and its determinant factors, vulnerability to food insecurity and coping strategies. Descriptive statistics and probit model were the analytical tools employed. The Value at Risk approach was used to analyze vulnerability to food insecurity in the study area. The descriptive statistics result indicates that there is high rate of food insecurity in Fedis district followed by Kersa. The vulnerability analysis also revealed that more households are to be food insecure in the future (40.5%) than present (37.3%), the case will be severe in Fedis district that changes from present (54%) to future (64%). Probit regression result shows that male headed households, per capita

income and climate change adaptation through changing planting dates are likely to augment food security. However, increase in household members and location (Fedis) is likely to reduce food security status of the households. The common strategies food insecure household use to mitigate and cope up with food security problems are building savings, accumulating assets, seeking alternative livelihood sources and reducing household consumption. Ojo *et al.* (2019) examined determinants of vulnerability to food insecurity among rural households in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The major objectives of the study were used to assess vulnerability to food insecurity status of the households and identify the factors affecting vulnerability. The Coping Strategy Index (CSI) and ordered logit regression was used the statistical tools used. Findings revealed that 35.33% of the households were moderately vulnerable, while 33.33% and 31.33% were mildly and severely vulnerable, respectively in the study area. Borrowing food, eating seed stock, begging for food and reducing meals were the major coping strategies adopted by the households. Regression results show that out of the 10 significant variables, age of household head, number of dependents, non-food expenditure and number of coping strategies positively influenced vulnerability while being married, educational level, farm income and off-farm occupation negatively influenced vulnerability to food insecurity among the households.

Ogunyemi *et al.* (2022) analyzed the extent of vulnerability to food insecurity and household coping mechanisms among yam farmers in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Multinomial logit (MNL) model and Feasible Generalized Least Square (FGLS) method were employed for the data analysis. The results of the FGLS model showed that 49.3% of the households were food secure and experienced low vulnerability to food insecurity. However, 30.23% of them were food insecure and highly vulnerable; they are considered as chronically food insecure households. Also, the study revealed that 11.01% of the food secure households may be food insecure in the future, if necessary, attention and intervention are not given by both households and the government. The findings of MNL revealed that the age of the household head, main occupation, household size, land size, net household income, and membership in a cooperative society were the main significant factors in yam farming households' decision to use coping strategies. Olawuyi and Ijila (2023) analyzed the correlates of farmers' resilience to food insecurity in South-West Nigeria. Descriptive statistics, the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA)'s food insecurity experience scale approach, composite score technique, principal component analysis (PCA) and Structural equation modeling (SEM) were used to analyze the data. The finding shows that more than half (55.3%) of the respondents were inadequate in almost all the resilience indicators and components, had low resilience capacity, and were vulnerable to food shocks and food insecurity. Mbuli *et al.* (2020) analyzes climate change and small Farmers' vulnerability to food insecurity in Cameroon Data were analyzed using an inductive thematic analysis approach. Results of the analysis revealed the key factors influencing small-scale farmers' vulnerability to climate change. High temperature and drought have exacerbated the risk of bush fires that destroy crops. Findings

revealed the complex interaction of economic, institutional, and climatic factors affecting small-scale farming in Cameroon.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data sources and description of variables

Secondary data was used for the study. The major source of data is the Nigeria General Household Survey panel component (GHS-Panel) obtained from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). the study covers a time range of 2012-2018 which involves 703 rural households randomly selected from the six geo-political zones in Nigeria. The variables used in the study include; food security, farming household income, farm size, access to resources, education, age, gender and household size, poor rain pattern, flooding, pest invasion, loss of properties due to rain intensity etc

Method of Analysis

Correlated random effects analytical technique was used to examine the effects of vulnerability to food insecurity on household farmers in Nigeria while descriptive statistics were used to describe the coping strategies against food insecurity employed by households in Nigeria. In statistics and econometrics, correlated random effects models are used to account for correlations between the random effects in a fixed-effects model. In these cases, the covariance matrix of the random effects was estimated (Mundlak, 1978).

The basic model can be expressed as follows:

$$Y_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1_{ij}} + \beta_2 X_{2_{ij}} + \dots + \beta_p * X_{p_{ij}} + u_i + \varepsilon_{ij} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

Y_{ij} is the Food Security

$X_{1_{ij}}, X_{2_{ij}} \dots X_{p_{ij}}$ are the p explanatory variables for the j-th observation within the i-th group,

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2 \dots, \beta_p$ are the fixed-effect coefficients associated with the explanatory variables

u_i represents the correlated random effect for the i-th group, and it follows a multivariate normal distribution with mean zero and covariance matrix D.

ε_{ij} is the residual error term for the j-th observation within the i-th group, assumed to be independent and normally distributed with mean zero and constant variance σ^2 .

The covariance matrix D of the correlated random effects depends on the underlying structure of the data and is often specified using variance and correlation parameters. D can be defined as:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma^2 & \rho\sigma^2 \\ \rho\sigma^2 & \sigma^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where:

σ_1^2 and σ_2^2 are the variances of the random effects at level 1 and level 2, respectively.

ρ_{12} is the correlation between the random effects at level 1 and level 2.

Summary statistics of the variables

Table 1 presents the summary statistics for key variables used in this study, based on dataset from waves 2-4 of as earlier mentioned. The key variables included household demographics (age, size, education), economic conditions (farm size, credit access), and various shocks (rainfall, flooding, pest invasion). From the results, the average household size is approximately 7 members, suggesting larger families which can possibly have a negative effect on households' food security status. Household heads' mean age was estimated as 50.46 years, reflecting a middle-aged demographic which can potentially influence households' ability to engage in farming practices due to its laborious nature. The average education level was approximately 7 years, indicating basic level of formal education, which may hinder the adoption of advanced farming techniques, and consequently farming output, thereby impacting households' food security status. The mean farm size was estimated as approximately 3 hectares. This is considered small given the country's population and the current food demand, and this could potentially limit food productivity and farm income. Credit access was found to be low, with only 7.97% of households accessing formal credit. This obviously restricts their ability to invest in agriculture or expand the current scale of operations.

Table 1: Relative Comparative Household Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents

Variables	Mean	Std.dev	Min	Max
Households size	6.889047	3.03994	1	28
Age	50.45804	15.26744	22	99
Education	6.470839	4.820001	0	16
Farm size	2.686316	2.483187	1	15
Informal credit	0.5803698	0.4938498	0	1
Formal credit	0.0796586	0.2709567	0	1
Vulnerability	0.3385491	0.4735532	0	1
Poor rainfall	0.200569	0.4007112	0	1
Flooding	0.0910384	0.2878685	0	1
Pest invasion	0.0753912	0.2642095	0	1
Less food	0.4679943	0.4993299	0	1
Limit food	0.4651494	0.4991391	0	1
Meal skip	0.3485064	0.4768366	0	1
Observation	703			

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4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Households vulnerability to food insecurity

Farmers were classified into their vulnerability status based on observed food insecurity. The distribution is shown in Table 2. The results indicated that 238 respondents, representing about one-third (33.85%) of the farming households were vulnerable to food insecurity while majority (465 respondents) which represent about 66.2% were found to be non-vulnerable to food insecurity in the study area. This tandem with Ojo *et al.* (2019) reported that 35.33% of the households were moderately vulnerable, while 33.33% and 31.33% were mildly and severely vulnerable, respectively in their study area.

Table 2: Profile household vulnerability to food insecurity

Vulnerability to food insecurity	Frequency	Percentage
Vulnerable	238	33.85
Non- vulnerable	465	66.15
Total	703	100.00

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Factors influencing food expenditure: Ordinary least square (OLS) and Fixed effect (FE) with covariates

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Fixed Effects (FE) analysis in table 3 provided significant insights into the factors affecting household food expenditure. The OLS model, with an R^2 of 0.8284, showed that various factors, including confectionery consumption, own food costs, purchased food expenses, household size, market distance, and meal-skipping, significantly increased food expenditure. Conversely, larger farm size, mode of land acquisition, and access to extension services were associated with lower food expenditure. The FE model further highlighted that purchased food expenses and dependency ratios positively impacted food expenditure at a 5% significance level, while flooding incidence negatively impacted expenditure at a 1% level. Variables like age, household size, land acquisition, and food borrowing were marginally significant. Flooding was noted to reduce total food expenditure, emphasizing how climate impacts food costs. Individual-specific factors explained 41.55% of the residual variance, underscoring their importance in household spending on food.

Table 3: Pooled of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Fixed effect (FE) with covariates

Variable	OLS Coef.	Regression Std. Err	t	FE Coef.	Regression Std. Err	t
Wave 4	0.0220421	0.0171341	1.29			
Confectioneries	0.0040606	0.001493	2.72	0.0017178	0.0025166	0.68
Own food cost	0.0068563	0.0018502	3.71	0.0021648	0.0022453	0.96
Purchased food	0.0000301	3.130007	96.03	0.5271457	0.2377708	2.22
Married	0.0278004	0.0227377	-1.22	-.0043084	0.0338448	-0.13
Sex	-0.0155635	0.012413	-1.25	0.0142668	0.0520759	0.27
Education	0.0018432	0.0012165	1.52	0.0006536	0.0021454	0.30
Household size	0.0222732	0.007797	2.86	-.6740066	0.3617081	-1.86
Dependency ratio	0.0077617	0.0137316	0.57	0.5244139	0.2374768	2.21
Distance nearest to market	0.2224603	0.073778	3.02	0.0001701	0.0076833	0.02
Formal credit	-.0212605	0.023601	-0.90	-.0098233	0.0246026	-0.40
Farm size	-.0126276	0.0040267	-3.14	-.0011442	.0028607	-0.40
Poor rainfall	0.0116438	0.0173163	0.67	.0253878	.0216941	1.17
Flooding	-.0131566	0.0306681	-0.43	.4800702	.1696582	2.83
Pest invasion	0.0228652	.0358674	0.64	.0048698	.036337	0.13
Land acquisition	-.0327804	0.0135627	-2.42	-.0201439	.0116819	-1.72
Extension	-.0223613	0.0116389	-1.92	-.3025867	.1804289	-1.68
Less Food	0.0154514	.0134847	1.15	.0135872	.0141572	0.96
Borrow Food	-.0096177	0.0152757	-0.63	-.6192335	.3226889	-1.92
Skip meal	-.5595906	0.2138112	2.62	-.0033354	.0128963	-0.26
Year 2015	-0.003693	0.0140402	-0.26	-.0050205	.0124369	-0.40
Year 2018	-.0076349	0.0140804	-0.54	-.066043	.0387594	-1.70
Zone 2	0.0263728	0.0208669	1.26			
Zone 3	-.7075948	0.433914	-1.63			
Zone 4	0.0123933	0.0188313	0.66			
Zone 5	0.0391286	0.02113	1.85			
Zone 6	-.0171883	0.0254783	-0.67			
_cons	0.615396	0.1245589	4.94	-1.01477	.3459644	-2.93
Num of obs	2,095			sigma_u	0.19043041	
Prob > F	0.0000			sigma_e	0.22588421	
R ²	0.8284			rho	0.41545211	
Adj. R ²	0.8261					

Source: Author's Computation 2024

Vulnerability to Food Insecurity: Correlated Random Effects (CRE) without covariates

The output of Random Effects (RE) model fitted without covariates is shown in Table 4. The Correlated Random Effects (CRE) model without covariates found that vulnerability alone has limited explanatory power for variations in household food expenditure, as shown by very low R-squared values (0.0031 for 2012, 0.0003 for 2015, and 0.0013 for 2018) and non-significant chi-square tests. However, vulnerability had a statistically significant positive effect on total food expenditure in 2012 (at 1% significance level) and in 2015 (at 10%), but it was not significant in 2018. A marginally significant positive impact was observed between 2015 vulnerability status and 2018 food expenditure, but not for 2018 vulnerability status itself. This suggests that households were more vulnerable to food expenditure in earlier years (2012 and 2015) compared to 2018, supporting findings that improved adaptive capacity to climate shocks over time has likely mitigated the effects of vulnerability on food expenditure.

Table 4: Correlated Random Effects (CRE) without covariates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Err	Z
Total Food Expenditure 2012			
Vulnerability 2012	1.999215	0.8000976	2.50
Vulnerability 2015	0.0672406	0.0394534	1.70
Vulnerability 2018	0.0421755	0.0472104	0.89
_cons	-2.255008	1.387265	-1.63
Total Food Expenditure 2015			
Vulnerability 2012	0.1713775	0.08026	2.14
Vulnerability 2015	0.0123979	0.0491919	0.25
Vulnerability 2018	-0.0161133	.048016	-0.34
_cons	-2.065362	0.834422	-2.48
Total Food Expenditure 2018			
Vulnerability 2012	-0.0299425	0.0481034	-0.62
Vulnerability 2015	.3215812	.176311	1.82
Vulnerability 2018	-0.0292568	0.0485108	-0.60
_cons	3.693847	0.6492354	5.69
	R ²	chi ²	
Total food expenditure 2012	0.0031	1.16	
Total food expenditure 2015	0.0003	0.18	
Total food expenditure 2018	0.0013	0.88	

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Vulnerability to Food Insecurity: Correlated Random Effects (CRE) with covariates

The results from the fitted Correlated Random Effects (CRE) model with covariates was presented in Tables 5, 6 and 7. The effects of vulnerability to food insecurity was observed in three waves (wave 2, wave 3 and wave 4). The model showed a significant improvement over CRE without covariates. The Correlated Random Effects (CRE) model with covariates significantly improved model accuracy, explaining 85%, 83%, and 84% of the variance in household food expenditure for 2012, 2015, and 2018, respectively.

The findings in table 5 revealed that vulnerability in 2012 had an insignificant positive effect on total food expenditure, while vulnerability in 2015 and 2018 had increasingly positive, though marginally or significantly, lagged effects on 2012 food expenditure. This suggests that vulnerability impacts on food expenditure accumulate over time, potentially reflecting delayed household adjustments to economic pressures. In 2012, own food costs and purchased food expenditure were highly significant, indicating that farming households not only produced their own food but also allocated more resources toward food purchases. Larger household sizes in 2012 correlated with higher food expenditure in 2018, suggesting that household composition has long-term impacts on food spending. Households that borrowed food or skipped meals in 2012 showed reduced food expenditure, pointing to temporary coping strategies in response to food insecurity. Education in 2012 had a lasting negative effect on 2018 food expenditure, implying that more educated households were able to manage food costs effectively in the long term. Furthermore, adverse climate events, such as poor rainfall in 2012, significantly increased food expenditure in 2015 and 2018. Similarly, flooding in 2012 led to increased food expenditure in 2015, aligning with Asfaw and Maggio's (2018) findings that climate shocks raise household food costs due to reduced agricultural productivity.

Table 5: Correlated Random Effects (CRE) with covariates: Total food expenditure 2012

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z	Coefficient	Std.Err	z
Total Food Expenditure 2012	2012			2015			2018		
Vulnerability	0.019263	0.0189052	1.02	0.1314508	0.0719789	1.83	0.0842796	0.0373158	2.26
Confectioneries	-0.0014625	0.0031191	-0.47	0.0019196	0.0035627	0.54	0.0063486	0.003333	1.90
Own food cost	0.0141996	0.0034396	4.13	0.0010497	0.0030535	0.34	0.0047596	0.0029438	1.62
Purchased food expenditure	4.995772	2.221267	2.25	0.120754	0.0393282	3.07	0.0648873	0.0331807	1.96
Age	-0.0002966	0.0006347	-0.47	-0.0002193	0.0006316	-0.35	-0.0010496	0.0006346	-1.65
Married	-0.0351735	0.0426281	-0.83	-0.4007235	0.1583986	-2.53	-0.0425588	0.0392	-1.09
Sex	-0.1669086	0.2618709	-0.64	-0.409673	0.1558047	-2.63	-0.4675926	0.1744617	-2.68
Education	0.003955	0.0025665	1.54	0.0007784	0.0027992	0.28	-1.151017	0.6526017	-1.76
Household size	0.0079247	0.0031462	2.52	0.0050222	0.0032012	1.57	1.65397	0.7690996	2.15
Formal credit	-0.0114537	0.0355716	-0.32	-0.0221631	0.0406368	-0.55	-0.0598751	0.0414593	-1.44
Farm size	0.0065389	0.0041948	-1.56	-0.0093115	0.0042685	-2.18	0.0020559	0.0038515	0.53
Poor rainfall	0.0482419	0.0273395	1.76	0.5156201	0.1675411	3.08	0.0259216	0.0309903	0.84
Flooding	0.0370754	0.0226751	1.64	-0.0546908	0.0523593	-1.04	-0.038809	0.0501998	-0.77
Pest invasion	0.0755116	0.0559347	1.35	0.1203958	0.06129	1.96	-0.0154369	0.0619658	-0.25
Land acquisition	-0.0079412	0.0225775	-0.35	-0.0240977	0.0226222	-1.07	-0.0330429	0.0221207	-1.49
Extension	1.722995	0.904982	1.90	-0.008481	0.0194246	-0.44	0.0089589	0.01914	0.47
Less food	-0.012919	0.0224597	-0.58	-0.0937808	0.0368731	-2.54	-1.758271	0.7709077	-2.28
Borrowing food	-0.1468342	0.0678972	-2.16	-0.0959676	0.0362573	-2.65	-0.0246134	0.0253588	-0.97
Skip meal	-0.3388719	0.1063758	-3.19	-0.0264591	0.0207991	-1.27	0.0023681	0.0204699	0.12
_cons	-0.0656368	0.0197502	-3.32						
Obs	Parms	RMSE	R ²	chi ²	P				
693	57	0.2391978	0.8508	3951.54	0.0000				

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Furthermore, table 6 showed that the vulnerability status in 2018 had a marginally positive impact on food expenditure in 2015, suggesting that households deemed vulnerable in 2018 were already incurring higher food costs in 2015. This finding aligns with research by Asfaw *et al.* (2021) on the prolonged effects of climate shocks on household welfare. Additionally, farming households' own food costs in 2012 and 2015, as well as purchased food expenses in 2012 and 2018, were strongly associated with increased food expenditures in 2015, highlighting a consistency in food spending patterns over time, as noted by Sibhatu and Qaim (2017). The analysis shows that older household heads in 2018 tended to have higher food expenditures in 2015, possibly due to household structure or consumption patterns, while education in 2018 reduced food expenditure in 2015, indicating efficient resource management by more educated households. Consistent with the findings of Kotu *et al.* (2022), access to formal credit in 2012 also significantly reduced 2015 food expenditures, likely due to diversified income sources or improved financial management.

Farm size in 2018 had a negative effect on 2015 food expenditure, suggesting that larger farms enhanced food self-sufficiency, thus lowering food costs. Climate events, such as flooding in 2012 and poor rainfall in 2015, significantly increased food expenditures in 2015, emphasizing the immediate cost impacts of climate shocks. Skipping meals in 2012 raised 2015 food expenditure, while skipping in 2018 reduced it, showing that coping strategies vary by period. Access to extension services in 2015 reduced 2015 food expenditure, reflecting the benefits of improved agricultural practices on household welfare. This result is consistent with the findings of Dercon *et al.* (2009) who also noted that, households with access to agricultural extension services spend less on food.

Table 6: Correlated Random Effects (CRE) with covariates: Total food expenditure 2015

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z
Total Food Expenditure 2015	2012			2015			2018		
Vulnerability	-0.0063368	0.0201235	-0.31	0.0107452	0.0210745	0.51	1.193288	0.7135757	1.67
Confectioneries	-0.0086038	0.0033202	-2.59	0.0053405	0.0037923	1.41	0.0058754	0.0035478	1.66
Own food cost	0.0111278	0.0036613	3.04	0.0071527	0.0032502	2.20	0.0052448	0.0031335	1.67
Purchased food expenditure	1.090656	0.357027	3.05	-0.0487027	0.0235606	-2.07	0.0486566	0.0233667	2.08
Age	-0.0003799	0.0006756	-0.56	0.0004557	0.0006723	0.68	0.7421828	0.2302503	3.22
Married	0.0141298	0.0453752	0.31	-0.0474117	0.0424561	-1.12	-0.0074761	0.0417262	-0.18
Sex	0.1387652	0.2787465	0.50	0.0125336	0.0689557	0.18	-0.1257607	0.2687958	-0.47
Education	-0.0005351	0.0027319	-0.20	-0.0002697	0.0029796	-0.09	-0.5920357	0.2263883	-2.62
Household size	0.0008949	0.0033489	0.27	0.0020427	0.0034075	0.60	1.178347	0.6131177	1.92
Formal credit	-0.077643	0.0378639	-2.05	-0.0429869	0.0432555	-0.99	0.0570827	0.044131	1.29
Farm size	-0.0057338	0.0044651	-1.28	-0.0068712	0.0045436	-1.51	-2.039165	0.8509828	-2.40
Poor rainfall	0.0127598	0.0291014	0.44	0.1017931	0.0309505	3.29	0.0201611	0.0329874	0.61
Flooding	0.0765451	0.0221484	3.46	0.0131464	0.0557335	0.24	0.0281617	0.0534348	0.53
Pest invasion	0.0002894	0.0595393	0.00	-0.0794047	0.0652397	-1.22	0.0386137	0.0215128	1.79
Land acquisition	0.0110143	0.0240325	0.46	-0.0463519	0.0240801	-1.92	-0.5525732	0.3288696	-1.68
Extension	-0.0323024	0.0208637	-1.55	-0.043199	0.0206764	-2.09	-0.0088393	0.0203734	-0.43
Less food	-0.0034302	0.0239071	-0.14	0.04485	0.0240767	1.86	0.0147906	0.0227696	0.65
Borrowing food	-0.0540016	0.0273537	-1.97	-0.0095455	0.0265683	-0.36	-0.0114561	0.026993	-0.42
Skip meal	0.0660951	0.0217587	3.04	-0.0228001	0.0221395	-1.03	-1.942158	0.6708792	-2.89
_cons	1.453087	0.2117804	6.86						
Obs	Parms	RMSE	R ²	chi ²	P				
693	57	0.2546123	0.8354	3518.16	0.0000				

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Table 7 shows that total food expenditure in 2018 was significantly influenced by past vulnerability and various household factors, which is agreement with the findings by Asfaw *et al.* (2021), Sibhatu and Qaim (2017). Households identified as vulnerable in 2012 had significantly higher food expenditures in 2018, indicating that early vulnerability had a lasting impact on expenses. Similarly, higher own food costs in 2012 and 2015 were positively associated with 2018 food expenditure, suggesting that households with higher initial food costs continued to experience elevated spending levels. Education in 2012 had a negative effect on 2018 food expenditure, implying that educated households were more efficient in managing long-term food costs. Household size in 2012 was positively associated with 2018 food expenditure, highlighting that larger households maintained higher food expenditures over time. Climate shocks, such as poor rainfall in 2012 and 2018, significantly increased 2018 food expenditure, showing the ongoing financial strain from environmental impacts. Conversely, households that borrowed or consumed less food in earlier years had lower food expenditures in 2018, possibly due to ongoing cost-cutting adaptations.

Other findings indicate that higher purchased food expenditure in 2015 led to increased spending in 2018, showing a persistence in spending habits. Marital status in 2015 had a negative impact on 2018 food expenditure, suggesting that household structure changes influenced spending. Access to formal credit in 2015 also reduced 2018 food expenditure, supporting the long-term financial benefits of credit. Larger farm sizes in 2015 were associated with lower 2018 food expenditure, likely due to improved self-sufficiency. Age and poor rainfall in 2018 had positive impacts on food expenditure, suggesting that older household heads and adverse weather conditions contributed to higher spending. Finally, land acquisition and extension services in 2018 reduced food expenditure, reflecting the economic benefits of land ownership and improved agricultural practices.

Table 7: Correlated Random Effects (CRE) with covariates: Total food expenditure 2018

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z	Coefficient	Std.Err	Z	Coefficient	Std.Err	z
Total Food Expenditure 2018	2012			2015			2018		
Vulnerability	0.4799357	0.1725416	2.78	0.0361203	0.0208427	1.73	0.0181084	0.0202354	0.89
Confectioneries	-0.0039426	0.0032836	-1.20	0.0047694	0.0037505	1.27	0.0065571	0.0035087	1.87
Own food cost	0.478496	0.1728298	2.77	0.0062697	0.0032145	1.95	0.0038532	0.003099	1.24
Purchased food expenditure	0.0227715	0.0397193	0.57	0.0722637	0.0214655	3.37	0.1678858	0.0706781	2.38
Age	0.0006755	0.0006681	1.01	0.0004376	0.0006649	0.66	0.0625938	0.0221131	2.83
Married	-0.0247949	0.044876	-0.55	-1.06051	0.3290835	3.22	0.0457783	0.0412672	1.11
Sex	0.0866484	0.2756803	0.31	0.0236191	0.0681972	0.35	-0.130669	0.265839	0.49
Education	-1.548905	0.4710116	-3.29	0.0023977	0.0029468	0.81	-2.465456	1.344749	1.83
Household size	2.181476	0.6888103	3.17	0.0014739	0.00337	0.44	2.636269	1.355911	1.94
Formal credit	-0.097559	0.0581011	-1.68	-1.981412	0.7127194	-2.78	0.0294768	0.0436456	0.68
Farm size	-0.0009613	0.004416	-0.22	-0.0621807	0.0231863	-2.68	0.0018615	0.0040546	0.46
Poor rainfall	0.4703212	0.1757743	2.68	-0.0406345	0.03061	-1.33	0.2903398	0.1208489	2.40
Flooding	0.0878392	0.0539176	1.63	0.3226854	0.1778373	1.81	0.0166518	0.052847	0.32
Pest invasion	-0.0538064	0.0588843	-0.91	0.0052189	0.0645221	0.08	0.021803	0.0652335	0.33
Land acquisition	-0.0093891	0.0237681	-0.40	-0.0002362	0.0238152	-0.01	-0.046314	0.0232872	-1.99
Extension	-0.3977104	0.1799435	-2.21	-0.0330397	0.0204489	-1.62	-0.061843	0.0222966	-2.77
Less food	-0.3760506	0.1814367	-2.07	-0.1471659	0.0413007	-3.56	0.0306766	0.0225191	1.36
Borrowing food	-1.187973	0.4498634	-2.64	-0.3119064	0.1792136	-1.74	-0.052669	0.020314	-2.59
Skip meal	0.0051926	0.0215193	0.24	-0.0134512	0.0218959	-0.61	-0.000855	0.0215493	-0.04
_cons	0.8592866	0.0803925	10.69						
Obs	Parms	RMSE	R ²	chi ²	P				
693	57	0.2518115	0.8430	3721.60	0.0000				

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Coping Strategies on Household Vulnerability to Food Insecurity

Coping strategies is an adjustment or self-insurance pursued by farmers to minimize the effects of food insecurity. Farmers adopt various coping strategies to reduce the impact of food insecurity, as shown in Table 8. The most common strategies included consuming lower-quality food (46.80%), managing limited food supplies (46.51%), reducing portion sizes (35.28%), skipping meals (34.85%), and prioritizing children’s meals (17.50%). These choices indicate moderate adjustments to maintain food security, with less than half of households relying on these approaches. Less common but more severe strategies included borrowing food (12.80%), having no food (11.24%), and sleeping hungry (9.25%). The relatively low use of these extreme measures suggests that while mild to moderate food insecurity persists, most households do not face severe deprivation. This pattern aligns with the findings of Hyacinth and Kwabena’s (2014) which noted that households’ responses to food insecurity in Nigeria is associated with several coping and adaptive strategies such as reducing portion sizes, skipping meals, consuming lower-quality food highlighting the effectiveness of adaptive strategies in managing food shortages.

Table 8: Distribution of Households based on Coping Strategies (n=703)

Strategies	Frequency	Percentage
Consume less quality food		
Yes	329	46.80
No	374	53.20
Limit food available		
Yes	327	46.51
No	376	53.49
Reduction of size of food eaten		
Yes		
No	248	35.28
Skip meal	455	64.72
Yes		
No	245	65.15
Children eaten first	458	34.85
Yes		
No	123	17.50
Borrowing food	580	82.50
Yes		
No	90	12.80
No food at all	613	87.20
Yes		
No	79	11.24
Sleeping hungry	624	88.76
Yes		
No	65	9.25
	638	90.75

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5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, food insecurity remains widespread among Nigerian farming households, with vulnerability decreasing slightly over time, potentially due to advancements in agricultural technology. There are both immediate and lasting impacts of food insecurity experiences on household food expenditure patterns across different years while households employed various coping strategies, their usage rate is less than 50%, indicating that mild to moderate food insecurity still persists.

It is recommended that food security strategies should be done. The strategies should include access to affordable improved farm inputs, improved training, storage to mention a few. Government should establish social investment program that involves providing food for the vulnerable in other to eradicate mild to moderate food insecurity.

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